

CREATING AN ONLINE ECOSYSTEM FOR CONSTRUCTION: THE MARKETPLACE APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

We are facing several problems in purchasing and supplying construction materials in Uzbekistan. This article provides information about a platform that centralizes the purchasing of construction materials, optimizes the delivery system, and enhances service efficiency.

KEYWORDS: Construction Marketplace, Digital Supply Chain, Procurement Efficiency, E-commerce, Construction Industry, Uzbekistan, Sourcing Challenges, Technological Integration, Sustainability, Infrastructure Development

INTRODUCTION

Construction is a booming economic sector with tremendous potential: it is projected to be a \$1.5 trillion global industry by 2027. The industry has been slow to digitize, with most companies still depending on paper catalogs and manual

order processes. This is starting to change, though, as more construction companies begin to appreciate the compelling reasons for embracing digitization or risk falling behind their rivals[4].

The e-Commerce segment of the building materials market has been going through tremendous growth since its recovery from the recession started in 2009. Specifically, the highest growth rates within the construction industry have been seen in the marketplaces due to the new market players and suppliers looking for improved trading conditions. These platforms aggregate the advantages of eliminating the need to maintain a dedicated site, with streamlined payment and shipping processes, and marketing assistance[3].

Not only is the building materials industry economically viable, but it also has strong growth potential. It is projected that by 2024, the global market share will reach \$1.7 trillion, with North America and Europe having substantial shares of \$319 billion and \$210 billion, respectively. The industry is forecast to grow by a further \$159 billion over the next five years [5]. That growth demonstrates long-term value in investing in a building materials startup—especially in an ever-more-digitized marketplace.

A strategic framework is necessary for the establishment of a successful online marketplace for construction materials and services. In this framework, proper planning extends from initial research and design to development and launch and further to its continuous management. The benefits and characteristics, besides the developmental strategies and overcoming the potential hurdles, are imperative to understand in order to build a successful and rewarding marketplace[6].

Despite a notable increase in exports, inefficiencies in logistics hinder the competitiveness of construction businesses. A digital platform tries to handle these challenges by centralizing the procurement process, optimizing delivery systems, and uniting the management of vehicles and improving the channels of communication between employees and clients for better efficiency within Uzbekistan's construction industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Technical challenges

Developing a construction-focused digital marketplace in Uzbekistan comes with its set of technical challenges. One of the most important ones is integration within an ecosystem. The past decade has seen significant development in digital solutions for the construction industry, from isolated solutions focused on addressing core needs to more holistic approaches in recent years.

"However, integration of all these point solutions into comprehensive suites is still a big challenge [7]." The Global Industry Council points out other

challenges such as rationalization and standardization, building digital talent, securing digital adoption, establishing value and return on investment [8]. Additionally, there is a concern about user experience. Construction material buyers tend to buy frequently; some even place orders daily through B2B e-Commerce sites. They are greatly interested in features such as simplified repeat ordering and one-click checkouts. A poor user experience, the lack of real-time product availability details, and no provision for payment terms means most buyers abandon their purchases and switch to more tech-savvy suppliers[9]. Addressing these user experience challenges is critical to ensure customer loyalty and the success of the marketplace.

The digital supply chain also plays an important role in the transformation of the construction industry. A digital supply chain can provide connectivity across the value chain and ecosystem, allowing multiple data sources to create transparency, provide advanced planning, and predict and avoid future problems. However, such capabilities have to be enabled by engineering and construction organizations to harvest their full potential[10][11][12].

Prioritized Features for Seamless Experience

In an online construction marketplace, some primary features need to be highlighted to ensure a seamless experience for both suppliers and users. First, the user experience is of utmost priority; features like easy repeat ordering and one-click checkout facilities are instrumental in encouraging fast and effective transactions [15]. Features like this make it easier for the user to complete multiple orders every week or even daily.

The market platform should foster an ecosystem built on cooperation and openness. The platform can help to promote healthy competition and simplify the procurement procedure in term of connecting different stakeholders like suppliers, contractors, architects, and engineers. The system does not only benefit the buyer with a wide range of choices but also provides the vendors with a better way of marketing their products and services [16].

Best Practices in Development

Creating a web portal for construction services, certain primary attributes need to be underlined in order to generate a perfect experience for both the providers and the end-users.

Initially, it is essential to formulate a concise message that aligns with the preferences of your desired clientele. This process encompasses identifying your target demographic, developing a message customized to their specific needs, and ensuring its effective delivery to this audience[13]. Within the framework of a construction marketplace, your target audience might consist of contractors, project managers, architects, and real estate developers. Gaining insights into their distinct

requirements and challenges will facilitate the creation of features that directly respond to these concerns.

DISCUSSION

Sourcing Challenges

The procurement of materials and equipment for construction initiatives in Uzbekistan is accompanied by a range of significant challenges. Although the construction materials sector has experienced considerable modernization and technological advancement in recent years, contractors continue to encounter difficulties in securing a reliable and competitive supply of materials[17].

Investments of \$9 billion over the past seven years were made through Government programs that resulted in the formation of almost 5,000 new companies. Thus, this capital injection managed to create 94,000 permanent jobs. Similarly, capital injection managed to increase production of building materials and reduced imports of building materials from 31% to 25%, with the inclusion of new products worth \$650 million[18].

Also, the impulse towards sustainable infrastructure development together with the adoption of new construction methods like Building Information Modelling and modular construction requires the industry to be constantly adaptive. Since such trends enhance both effectiveness and sustainability of the industry, they, at the same time, force contractors to navigate through an environment whose transformation in elements of technological advancement and regulatory frameworks is rapidly increasing[19].

The swift increase in Uzbekistan's population, which is anticipated to attain 50 million individuals by the year 2050, highlights the pressing necessity for the development of residential infrastructure and urban planning initiatives. This demographic transition exerts additional stress on the procurement of materials and equipment, while simultaneously necessitating enhancements in the energy efficiency of current buildings to meet the requirements of new construction projects[20]. The strategic objectives outlined in Presidential Decree No.

UP-5963 aims at revolutionizing the construction sector through innovative solutions, advancing urban planning, and facing the core challenge of reconciling development with sustainable practices[21].

Impact on Traditional Supply Chain

The construction of the e-platform for construction materials, equipment, and labor purchase is believed to fundamentally change the dynamics of traditional supply chains in Uzbekistan. No doubt, the E&C industry has undergone huge challenges in the recent past, especially through the times of supply chain disruptions coupled with volatile costs related to equipment and materials.

Companies able to adapt tactical solutions in this aspect are likely to emerge stronger and better prepared to handle future uncertainties [22].

Delays in supply chains, mostly due to the COVID-19 pandemic, have impacted nearly every industry, with the construction industry being one of the most affected. Material shortages and labor deficits have forced contractors to adapt by finding alternative materials and improving communication with suppliers[23]. These disruptions have highlighted the need for better and more transparent management of supply chains.

The construction industry, while adept at completing complex projects, has faced inefficiencies and exposure to economic volatility, a condition only worsened by the pandemic[24]. Surging global transportation costs and domestic delivery delays have exacerbated material shortages, thus hiking project costs and timelines.

The shortages in the labor force, particularly in logistics sectors, have exacerbated delays, emphasizing the vital requirement for a smoother supply chain process[25]. Digital technologies are leading a systemic transformation within the construction industry. Digital supply chains help manufacturers and suppliers optimize their processes, communicate more effectively with their partners, and smooth operations across all stages of production. These bring in a host of benefits, including increased transparency, better planning, and predictive capabilities that can ward off potential problems [26]. However, this integration is still in its infancy as most contractors are just starting to centralize and automate their supply chain activities[27].

U.S. builders continue to face high prices due to ongoing material shortages and increased logistics and labor costs, which are further exacerbated by global conflicts that add new instability[28]. A similar situation can be observed in Uzbekistan, where the creation of an online marketplace may mitigate some of those, creating a centralized procurement channel, thus potentially bringing greater stability of costs and supply chain performance. The adoption of e-procurement practices brings along a host of opportunities and challenges. While offering various advantages, such as high efficiency and reduced costs, there are numerous barriers to the effective implementation of a digital supply chain. Some barriers include problems related to technology adoption, the need for human capital development, and integration of new systems with the existing business processes [29].

Transition Challenges

The major Challenges in the transition of Uzbekistan's construction industry towards an e-marketplace are manifold. A major concern is definitely the need for good infrastructure and technological resources to host this type of platform. The

gradual change of Uzbekistan from a centrally planned economy into a market-based system has faced various development challenges, which impact the efficacy of emerging technological solutions [32]. The existing technological architecture may not have the required strength to support an online marketplace's needs and hence may lead to inefficiencies and disturbances.

Besides, the existing infrastructure in Uzbekistan itself represents a high energy consumption, which requires urgent improvement in energy efficiency and sustainable urban development[31]. The requirements of such nature increase the complexity of the transition because the digital marketplace shall embed those advanced technologies and strategies supporting energy-efficient construction practices.

Economic factors are another challenge. While the e-commerce sector in Uzbekistan is seeing rapid growth — \$311 million in 2022 —and is expected to maintain a strong growth trend [30], the construction industry has seen slower development. Given the construction sector contributed only 0.4% to GDP growth in 2022, companies might feel less financial incentive to make the switch towards moving into an online marketplace, especially within an uncertain economic environment formed by exogenous factors such as higher costs of food, energy, and logistics[35].

Finally, there are policy and regulatory challenges. Governmental policies and expenditures largely determine the parameters within which the construction sector in Uzbekistan operates. These policies can either support or hinder the transition to an online marketplace[31]. Navigation of these regulations and staying compliant can be a complex and time-consuming task for any organization involved in bringing about this change.

A multi-pronged approach will be followed for the mitigation of challenges: investment in technological infrastructure, comprehensive training of the workforce, and close collaboration with governmental bodies to ensure supportive policies and regulations. Besides, one can also use experiences and resources from international partners involved in supporting economic development—the Asian Development Bank, the World Bank—to obtain valuable insights and help in this respect[32][33][34].

RESULTS

Benefits and Efficiency

The construction industry in Uzbekistan will greatly benefit from the creation of a digital marketplace that combines all available resources, such as labor, equipment, materials, and technologies. Globally, the construction industry faces challenges such as projects generally taking 20 percent longer to be completed and going over budget by up to 80 percent[38]. A digital marketplace

shall potentially reduce these inefficiencies through better project management and resource allocation.

Such a marketplace would bring along quite a number of advantages, one being the provision for increased efficiency and productivity. Digital tools, such as BIM software, help manage information throughout the lifecycle of a built asset. BIM helps integrate data throughout the value chain, enabling information to flow smoothly from design through to construction and operations.

Past experiences show that even when pilot initiatives using new technologies are successful, replication of those solutions usually faces challenges when appropriate adoption and training are not ensured.

Case studies

Construction in Ghana plays a very vital role in the economic development by contributing 13.7% to the GDP, stimulating growth at various aspects of its industries like infrastructure, roads, water supply, and electricity. It also generates employment, which is an essential factor in countries with a high unemployment rate just like Ghana. Considering the benefits it would bring into developing countries like Uzbekistan, a certain digital platform created for construction can be integrated with such resources as workforce, equipment, materials, and technology. This approach draws on the successful strategies of other countries where the construction industry has been a prime mover in economic and social development[1].

CONCLUSION

Establishing the online marketplace for construction in Uzbekistan thus provides enormous opportunities to help the industry overcome its present inefficiencies. This would also provide consolidation into one platform of the processes relating to purchase, delivery, and communication, thereby helping in price stabilization of materials, rationalization of the supply chain, and enabling better collaboration among the network of stakeholders. In this respect, project management-optimizing digital tools like BIM and digital supply chains offer various prospects for lessening the time overruns of projects and enhancement in supply-chain transparency. Although the development of such marketplaces does have challenges, which include technological infrastructure, adaptation by the workforce, and regulatory compliance issues, a well-implemented marketplace has the potential to disrupt the industry by enhancing productivity and hence contributing to sustainable growth. The way to competitive advantage in the construction sector in Uzbekistan will lead through the adoption of best international practices in platform design and the resolution of issues with sourcing and logistics, which again are factors to contribute to long-term economic development and improvement in the standards of the industry.

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